

SITES OF REMEMBERING

Landscapes, Lessons,
Policies

Vikas Lakhani
Eveline de Smalen

Transformations in
Environment and Society

2018 / 3

RCC Perspectives: Transformations in Environment and Society is an open-access publication that exists to record and reflect the activities of the Rachel Carson Center for Environment and Society. The journal provides a forum for examining the interrelationship between environmental and social changes and is designed to inspire new perspectives on humanity and the wider world. *RCC Perspectives* aims to bridge the gap between scholarly and non-scholarly audiences and encourage international dialogue.

All issues of *RCC Perspectives* are available online. To view past issues, please visit www.environmentandsociety.org/perspectives.

SPONSORED BY THE

Federal Ministry
of Education
and Research

Sites of Remembering

Landscapes, Lessons, Policies

Edited by

Vikas Lakhani
Eveline de Smalen

RCC Perspectives

Transformations in Environment and Society

2018 / 3

Vikas Lakhani and Eveline de Smalen

Introduction: Using Memory Studies in Environmental Policy

In the winter of 2018, a substantial environmental controversy dominated public debate in the Netherlands. Over the course of an unusually cold winter, the Oostvaardersplassen, a nature reserve that has been a Ramsar wetland of international importance since 1989 and a Natura 2000 site since 2010, saw the death of a high number of its large herbivores due to lack of food. The management of the Oostvaardersplassen is largely in line with rewilding practices, and intervention is kept to a minimum. For years, this conviction has clashed with the popular opinion that suggested that, since the Oostvaardersplassen are located in a polder that was reclaimed only in 1968 and are not connected to any larger reserves, they cannot be considered *nature*. Its managers, therefore, have a responsibility to care for the animals living in the area, including feeding them to keep them from starvation. In 2018, this debate escalated and led to protests, private feeding initiatives, and death threats addressed to foresters, until the province was forced to deviate from the management plan and feed the animals.

This case exemplifies both the challenge and importance of policymaking that acknowledges the complexities of relations between people and their environment. Public institutions must strive towards sustainable long-term planning, formulating flexible and inclusive policies, and encouraging two-way communication with different stakeholders. In this way, they gain legitimacy for their policy while simultaneously legitimizing people's experience. This is exactly the process that led to the European Union's becoming one of the world's leading actors in environmental regulation in the 1990s. The EU's engagement with environmental policy was a response to increasing environmental concern amongst its citizens, and creating legislation was seen as an opportunity to enhance the EU's legitimacy.¹

Environmental regulations have always been dependent on memories and narratives. A key challenge for ecologists and environmental activists advocating for conservation of the Wadden Sea in the mid-twentieth century, which today is also a Natura 2000

1 R. Daniel Kelemen and David Vogel, "Trading Places: The Role of the United States and the European Union in International Environmental Politics," *Comparative Political Studies* 43 no. 4 (2010), 427–56, esp. 443–4.

site, was the fact that a legacy of disregard, honed over millennia² obstructed an appreciation of the Wadden Sea as a place of value. In their campaigns, which proved to be effective, it was vital that they “reframe[d] the Wadden Sea scientifically, visually, and narratively.”

The European Commission recognizes that “Europe faces huge challenges in reducing inequality and social exclusion.”³ In this age of climate change, pollution, environmental degradation, and increasing risk of extreme weather events and disasters, these challenges cannot be disentangled from the physical environment. To enhance inclusive, innovative, and reflective societies and to foster resilient communities, environmental management has to be treated with sensitivity to its citizens’ memories, identities, and cultural heritage, and vice versa.

The increasing risk of disaster due to changing climate and unsustainable environmental management practices is particularly pertinent to this volume, in which many papers focus on disasters specifically. In times of crisis, public institutions often assume that emotion-laden communities do not act rationally and need assistance in evaluating themes of importance and meaning for a complete recovery. However, these institutions can underestimate the value of emotions and affect. Roberto E. Barrios argues that governments need to formulate policies that take emotion and affect into account.⁴ If institutions fail to do so, their policies run the risk of rejection by affected communities. The authors in this volume argue that public institutions that recognize the complexities of remembering and forgetting have better chances of formulating effective policies. Similarly, the voices of marginalized groups, which are too often not heard but can offer a different perspective that is important for developing holistic responses to events, need to be acknowledged. Sites of change are unique, both environmentally and socially, and failure to recognize this can create new problems. For instance, the state government of Maharashtra adopted a village for reconstruction after the Gujarat earthquake in India in 2001 but relocated the entire village to a low-lying area, which gets flooded with salt water every year. As a result,

2 Christian Jouanin, cited by Anna-Katharina Wöbse in, “Space, Place, Land, and Sea: The ‘Ecological Discovery’ of the Global Wadden Sea,” in *Spatializing the History of Ecology: Sites, Journeys, Mappings*, eds. Raf de Bont and Jens Lachmund, 204–222 (New York: Routledge, 2017); 205.

3 European Commission, “Europe in a Changing World,” <http://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/europe-changing-world-inclusive-innovative-and-reflective-societies> (accessed 31 May 2018).

4 Roberto E. Barrios, *Governing Affect: Neoliberalism and Disaster Reconstruction* (Lincoln; London: University of Nebraska Press) 2017.

the newly constructed houses deteriorated within a few years and the dilapidated village stands without a single inhabitant.

This volume addresses the specific ways in which memories can contribute to effective policymaking. It presents a diverse selection of case studies that show that for policies to be effective, they need to be based on participation, collaboration, and coordination. In the wide range of disciplines it includes, the volume also implicitly showcases the usefulness of interdisciplinarity: different disciplines can offer different insights and solutions, and together they can provide a wide overview of how to account for social cohesion and critical heritage in the move forward to addressing the environmental issues society faces today. Based on findings from 11 essays on a wide variety of case studies, the editors suggest three recommendations:

Recommendation 1: Acknowledge the existence and relevance of counternarratives

Recommendation 2: Utilize citizens' memories as a source of local knowledge

Recommendation 3: Support resilience in communities by recognizing the role of both remembering and forgetting

For elaborations on these, see the "Recommendations for Policymakers" section at the end of this volume.

We acknowledge that these recommendations are broad in nature: we maintain that this is necessary so they are relevant to and can be applied in different contexts, and can be translated into specific actionable strategies on a case-by-case basis. These strategies can then be tailored to the relevant communities and environments in which they will be applied. We do not claim to present the intricacies and complexities of policymaking in this volume, but we offer insights from academic research that can contribute to a richer understanding of effective conservation and management practices.

